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Review Article

Herbal Contour Stick: A Natural Approach to Sculpting and Skincare- A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

Herbal face contour is a natural skin care product that combines herbal essential oils to enhance facial definition, reduce fine lines and wrinkles and improve skin texture. Herbal contour product typically focuses on using natural ingredients for defining the shape and reduces the appearance of cellulite. Herbal contour products are natural alternative to traditional makeup contouring product these product not only help define and sculpt the face but also provide nourishing benefit for the skin. Users generally appreciate the natural formulation, which can be gentler on skin compared to synthetic options. Many report a pleasant scent and a soothing application experience. It is rich in antioxidant and vitamins. Herbal contour product aim to promote a healthy complexion while reducing the risk of irritation associated with synthetic option herbal contouring emphasizes both aesthetics and skin health. Herbal face contour have gained popularity due to their natural ingredients and potential benefits for skin health. Facial contouring products have become increasingly popular and complex, making knowledge of facial anatomy crucial for achieving deserved outcome without complications. The growing demand for natural and sustainable cosmetic products has enhanced the interest in herbal formulations for contouring application. The reports a lab process and development of the herbal contour cream using herbal natural ingredients that are known to enhance skin toning. Jojoba oil were among the key herbal factors chosen for skin moisturization and antioxidant action as well as the non-comedogenic characteristic of the carrier. Overall using herbal and natural ingredients often provide additional benefits and creating a move effortless and glowing look, while both synthetic and natural can achieve similar aesthetic results, overall using herbal contour product align with a holistic approach to beauty, focusing on health, sustainability and natural aesthetics.

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INTRODUCTION

According to the D & C Act in 1940, any articles intended to be rubbed, poured, sprinkled, sprayed or applied to part of human body for cleansing, beautifying, promoting attractiveness or altering the appearance and includes articles intended for use as cosmetics. (Yadav et al., 2022) Herbal product includes oils, extracts etc., Herbal cosmetics played an important role in women's life because the cosmetics produce increases the beauty of them the Herbal material product reaches the high trend in beauty and fashion. The Herbal products are softest without any side effect in these preparations we have studied the properties of Herbal contour. (Mithal & Saha, 2000) Women use contour most frequently among cosmetics for beautiful face appearance, women's apparent facial characteristics can be altered with contour. Herbal contour sticks are typically produced as molded sticks and are made up of coloring natural pigments and also made up of mixtures of oil, waxes etc. These were only a few shades of synthetic contour available in the early 20th century, contour comes in different types i.e., compact contour form is used and applied.

Contour background:

Contouring has become more popular trends that we have added to our beauty. It was first invented during the Elizabethan era in 1500 made modern by Drag queen and then later the Kardashians. Contouring is used to exaggerate and transform one's bone structure. Back in Elizabethan England, stage actors would contour their face with the chalk and stood to see their facial expressions in 16th century to 19th century.

Advantages Of Herbal Cosmetics Over Synthetic Cosmetics:

These days, herbal cosmetics are free of artificial substances, have no harmful side effects, and give the body nutrients that promote health, herbal cosmetics are now preferred over synthetic ones. Compared to synthetic cosmetics, natural cosmetics are safer, body-compatible, naturally occurring, and affordable, offer a variety of goods, have no adverse effects, and are not tested on animals. (Hole et al., 2024)

Characteristics Of Herbal Contour

- 1) Long lasting effect.
- 2) Stable physically and chemically.
- 3) Shining and smooth appearance.
- 4) Make contour smooth and soft.

Figure 1 Anatomy of face

Classification Of Skin

Table no. 01

Types	Score	Skin Colour	Effect To Uva	Reaction To Sun	Skin Tone
I	0-6	Caucasian, blond/red hair, freckles, fair skin, blue eyes	Very sensitive	Always burns, never tans	Very fair
II	7-13	Caucasian	Very sensitive	Usually burn, tans minimally	Fair
III	14-20	Darker Caucasian, light Asian	sensitive	Burns moderately, tans Uniformly	Fair to medium
IV	21-27	Mediterranean, Asian, Hispanic	Moderately sensitive	Rarely burns, always tans well	Medium
V	28-34	Middle Eastern, Latin, light-skinned black, Indian	Minimally Sensitive	Very rarely burns, tans very easily	Olive or dark
VI	35-36	Dark-skinned black	Least sensitive	Never burn, always tans	Very dark

Benefits Of Natural Contour Over Existing Synthetic Ones

- Herbal extends are non toxic, highly lipophilic, antioxidant and anti-micro trial, anti-

inflammatory and are used especially for skin conditions.

- Colorant has different original colors from Brownish red, dark blue, deep brown and in all shades of brown.

- In these colours, with different combinations, other shades can be found.

Uses Of Contour Other Than The Face

- Contouring can be used in neck and jaw line to define it and help blend the face contouring for a seamless look.
- It can also be used in collarbone and shoulder chest and also add some more dimensions to the décolletage areas for glamorous look.
- To define muscles for toned appearance it used to contour Arms and legs.
- Contouring knuckles can make fingers and hands appearance longer and slimmer's.

Safe To Use

- Contouring to the face and essential parts, it mostly depends on the product and their use.
- They should be non-comedogenic formula i.e., will not clog the pores
- Using escam (liquid based contour for dry skin and powder based for oily or combination skin.
- By avoiding harmful ingredients.
- Patch testing is important to avoid the irritation before applying the product.

Type Of Contour

Makeup contour includes stick form, liquid form and powders form and cream form.

- 1) **Stick contour:** - It is a type of contour that can be used to sculpt and define the face features and can be used to create an illusion effect and depth.
- 2) **Liquid contour:** - It is used to shape the face proper and also provide nourishment and moisturizes the dry skin type.

3) **Powder contour:** - This formula can be easily applied and gets easily merge with skin gives natural look and highlight effect.

4) **Cream contour:** - It blends smoothly on the skin and making the dry, combination skin in good condition and gives glamorous effect.

Face Disorder Where Contour Uses To Enhance Its Sculpt

1) **Swelling:** - Face swelling can be cause by an allergic reaction. Sensitivity to specific foods or beverages, medications, cosmetic or airborne allergens could be cause of the reaction. The face usually return to normal when the cause is found and removed, but the reason behind the swelling is often still unknown. Hereditary angioedema is a condition that can result in at time of swelling. Face swelling may be brought on by non-hereditary disorders like erythematous multiform, sunburn, cold, dry weather or trauma.(McMullen, 2024)

2) **Discoloration:** - Face discoloration can occur as a result of fungal infection, iron deficiency anemia, sun exposure, or an allergic reaction.

3) **Sun damage:** - Sun damage can cause the face to become dry and hard. A white, filmy appearance or red spots indicate damage that raises the risk of developing cancer again. Wearing a wide-brimmed hat to protect the face from the sun's harmful rays or applying sunscreen can help prevent this kind of damage.(Kolarsick et al., 2011)

4) **Acne scale or pitted skin:** - Contouring help distract from uneven texture.

5) **Facial asymmetry:** - It creates the illusion of balance between uneven sides of the face. i.e., jaw line, cheekbone or forehead.

Herbal Ingredients of Contour

➤ Bases

A significant class of ingredients for produces of cosmetic and personal hygiene goods is waxes. Wide range of product and industries used waxes. Although their main use is in cosmetics, food, pharmaceuticals and as natural alternative to synthetic waxes. They are also widely used as thickeners or emulsifier in all aspects. In chemical terms, waxes are complex combinations of fatty acids, hydrocarbon and esters. In natural terms, waxes are intimately derived from natural sources such as living plants and animals. They are resistant to bacteria's, oxidation and moisture.(Krendlinger & Wolfmeier, 2022)

➤ Oils

There are physical differences between oils and fats. Triglycerides, another name for fats and oils, are chemically glycerol esters made up of fatty acids and glycerol; the latter is typically solid at room temperature. The stability and characteristics of the oils are determined by the saturated and unsaturated state of fatty acids. Oils are concentrated extracts of various plants. Oils are used in aromatherapy for their scent and potential therapeutic effects. They are used in skin care and hair care products for their moisturizing and nourishing properties. Carrier oils are used to dilute essential oils for topical application, such as coconut oil, jojoba oil, almond oil, lavender oil.(Blaak & Staib, 2022)

➤ Colouring agents

The primary purpose of colourants, also known as colouring agents, is to give cosmetics goods a unique look. Since ancient time, color has been a part of cosmetics. Sight, touch and smell work together to impact a person's desirers to purchase

cosmetics. Color is therefore an essential component of cosmetic formulation. The colourants derived from natural sources should be non toxic with no physiological activity. It should be a definite chemical compound because then only its colouring power will be reliable. Its tinctorial power should be high enough so that only small quantities would be sufficient for use. Colourants should be unaffected by light, tropical temperature, hydrolysis, microorganism and therefore they must be stable on storage.(Anjali & Nardev, 2016)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the last few decades, the use of cosmetics has been tremendously increased, and the chemical involved for formulating these cosmetics cause hazards to user health. However, the aim of present research work was formulation and evaluation of herbal contour, with a goal to minimize the side effects of the available synthetic contour in the market. Hence, from the result obtained in the present investigation shows that the herbal formulation has a better option with minimum side effects.

CONCLUSION

Study concluded that herbal contour can be successfully formulated using different natural ingredients. It is also concluded the use of natural colorant in contour formulation having very less or no side effect. In this work, we found excellent properties of herbal contour and further studies are needed to be performed to ascertain more useful benefits of herbal contour as cosmetics. As the use of synthetic agents can cause allergies and be found to have carcinogenicity. The ability to crave the right makeup for you depends on accurate knowledge of the ingredients. Natural remedies are accepted nowadays with open hands as they are safer than chemical based products. Herbal

formulation are required in large amounts to fulfill the need of the growing world market. It is an effective attempt to formulate the herbal contour different natural nutrients.

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